

Goldbach variations

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Is every even integer $n \geq 4$ a sum of two odd ones? Let's see.

The set of these evens is the union of two disjoint sets:

$$E1 \equiv \{\text{twice evens}\} = \{2(2m), m = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots\} = \{4, 8, 12, 16, \dots\}$$

$$E2 \equiv \{\text{twice odds}\} = \{2(2m + 1), m = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots\} = \{6, 10, 14, 18, \dots\}$$

Thus halving any $n \in E2$ yields its odd summands $\{2m + 1, 2m + 1\}$; else, if $n \in E1$ its integer 2nd neighbors are

$$\{2(2m) - 2, 2(2m) + 2\}$$

and halving these produces its odd summands: $\{2m - 1, 2m + 1\}$.

Another method; first note that

$$\text{floor}(n - x) = n + \text{floor}(-x)$$

$$\text{ceiling}(n + x) = n + \text{ceiling}(x)$$

and that obviously $\text{floor}(-1/2) = -1$, while $\text{ceiling}(1/2) = 1$

Let's start with E1.

For $n = 2(2m)$, divide the 1st neighbors by 2, and use the 'floor' function on the left-neighbor and the 'ceiling' function on the right.

$$\text{Its 1}^{\text{st}} \text{ neighbors are } \{n - 1, n + 1\} = \{4m - 1, 4m + 1\}$$

Halving the left-neighbor followed by the 'floor' operation yields

$$\text{floor}((4m - 1)/2) = \text{floor}(2m - 1/2) = 2m + \text{floor}(-1/2) = 2m - 1$$

Halving the right-neighbor followed by the 'ceiling' operation yields

$$\text{ceiling}((4m + 1)/2) = \text{ceiling}(2m + 1/2) = 2m + \text{ceiling}(1/2) = 2m + 1$$

the same odd summands as above.

E2 is next; this time the operations are reversed.

For $n = 2(2m + 1)$, its 1st neighbors are $\{4m + 2 - 1, 4m + 2 + 1\} = \{4m + 1, 4m + 3\}$.

Now use the 'ceiling' function on the left-neighbor and the 'floor' function on the right. Thus

$$\text{ceiling}(1/2(4m + 1)) = \text{ceiling}(2m + 1/2) = 2m + \text{ceiling}(1/2) = 2m + 1$$

$$\text{floor}(1/2(4m + 3)) = \text{floor}(2m + 3/2) = 2m + \text{floor}(3/2) = 2m + 1$$